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**CAIRT mission product test data set descriptions for
case/impact studies for volcanic ash detection**

README-6

**Bianca Maria Dinelli¹, Enzo Papandrea¹, Umberto Rizza²,
Piera Raspollini³, Tiziano Maestri⁴, Guido Masiello⁵,
Stefano Corradini⁶**

¹**National Research Council of Italy-Institute of atmospheric sciences and climate (CNR-ISAC)**, *via P. Gobetti 101, 40129 Bologna, Italy*

²**National Research Council of Italy-Institute of atmospheric sciences and climate (CNR-ISAC)**, *strada Provinciale Lecce-Monteroni km.1.2, 73100 Lecce, Italy*

³**National Research Council of Italy-institute of Applied Physics "Nello Carrara"**, *via Madonna del Piano 10, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino, Firenze, Italy*

⁴**Department of Physics and Astronomy (DIFA) of the university of Bologna (UNIBO)**, *Viale Berti Pichat 6/2, 40127, Bologna*

⁵**School of Engineering of University of Basilicata (SI-UNIBAS)**, *via dell'Ateneo Lucano 10, 85100, Potenza, Italy*

⁶**National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, (INGV)**, *via di Vigna Murata 605, 00143, Roma, Italy*

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<i>Abstract</i> This document will describe the CAIRT L1b test data products for case/sensitivity studies for volcanic ash detection, as well as the auxiliary data needed for the forward model. The intent of this document is to be adopted as README for potential L1b users.		
The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.		
<i>Names of authors</i> Bianca Maria Dinelli, Enzo Papandrea, Umberto Rizza, Piera Raspollini, Tiziano Maestri, Guido Masiello, Stefano Corradini		
<i>ESA Technical Officer</i> Alex Hoffmann Division Mission Science Division Directorate Directorate of Earth Observation Programmes	<i>ESA budget heading</i>	

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List of acronyms

CAIRT	Changing-Atmosphere InfraRed Tomography
FOV	Field Of View
GBB	Geofit Broad Band
ILS	Instrument Line Shape
LOS	Line of Sight
KLIMA	Kyoto protocol-informed management of adaptation
TDS	Test Data Set
WRF	Weather Research & Forecasting Model
2D	2 dimensional

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This purpose of this document is to provide a description of the test data set (TDS) products that will be produced within the context of the CAIRT mission for case/sensitivity studies for volcanic ash detection work package. Only the spectral radiance datasets (L1b products) are described here.

The TDS produced for the simulations for CAIRT will be obtained with the GBB_clouds code (sect 1.3) using WRF-Chem outputs (sect 1.2).

1.2 WRF-Chem description and output file format

For this project, the WRF-Chem model version 4.3.1 (Grell et al., 2005) has been utilized in a numerical domain covering the central Mediterranean region, with 310×320 grid points and a horizontal grid spacing of 6 km (total extension 1854×1914 km²) on 39 pressure levels. This domain covers both the large-scale transport and the plume dispersion near the volcano (Rizza et al., 2023). CAIRT measurements will be then simulated in a region where CAIRT lines of sight intersect the ash plume.

Only a subset of the whole WRF-Chem output is needed for this study. Therefore, for convenience, a dedicated netCDF file has been created with the variables listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Structure of the WRF-Chem subset output file

Variable	Dimension	Description	Units
Time	1	Minutes since simulation start	
Lat	[south_north, west_east]	Latitude, south is negative	degree_north
Lon	[south_north, west_east]	Longitude, west is negative	degree_east
Hgt	[south_north, west_east]	Terrain height	m
T2	[south_north, west_east]	Temp at 2 m	K
Emiss	[south_north, west_east]	Surface emissivity	
Psf	[south_north, west_east]	Sfc pressure	Pa
Tsk	[south_north, west_east]	Surface skin temperature	K
Landmask	[south_north, west_east]	Land mask (1 land, 0 water)	
Qvapor	[bottom_top, south_north, west_east]	Water vapor mixing ratio	kg kg ⁻¹
p	[bottom_top, south_north, west_east]	Total pressure	Pa
tk	[bottom_top, south_north, west_east]	Temperature	K
zeta	[bottom_top, south_north, west_east]	Height	m
tk	[bottom_top, south_north, west_east]	Temperature	K
cldfra	[bottom_top, south_north, west_east]	Cloud fraction	
alt	[bottom_top, south_north, west_east]	Inverse density	m ³ kg ⁻¹
v1,...v10	[bottom_top, south_north, west_east]	Vash mixing ratio	ug/kg-dryair

1.3 The GBB_clouds description and output file format

The Geofit Broad Band (GBB)-clouds code adopts an approach called geo-fit (Carlotti et al., 2001) (Carlotti et al., 2006), which has been developed for analysing limb-scanning observations of the atmosphere from an orbiting platform. The Geo-fit approach fully accounts for the horizontal inhomogeneity of the atmosphere, with the aim of retrieving atmospheric parameters from the simultaneous analysis of observations taken along the whole orbit. Thus, the Geo-fit forward model is 2-dimensional and able to simulate measurements along a full orbit. Being a 2D code, it assumes the atmospheric variability only along the satellite track (and not in the cross-track direction), and therefore in the orbit plane (the plane that includes the full orbit track).

The forward model adopted by the GBB_clouds code was validated more than two decades ago using limb-scanning measurements simulated for a full MIPAS orbit (Carlotti et al., 2001) and afterwards verified with real data in the frame of the MIPAS-SM Project (Grassi and Carlotti, 2004). More recently, a nadir version of the GBB code was described and extensively validated against the Kyoto protocol-informed management of adaptation (KLIMA) code (Dinelli et al., 2024).

The spectra are computed on a very dense frequency grid (0.001 cm⁻¹) that in a separate study was found to be adequate to capture the shape of very thin emission lines, typical of high-altitude pressures/temperatures. Then, the resulting spectra have been convoluted with both the ISRF and FOV

The following instrumental parameters, resulting from CAIRT MRD, have been adopted for the case studies:

- CAIRT spectral resolution is 0.2 cm⁻¹ (corresponding to a maximum optical path difference of the interferometric slide 2.5 cm), which was the assumption at the time we performed the simulations. The spectra are Norton-Beer strong apodized for this resolution.
- FOV function is of 1.4 FWHM.
- Simulations performed in the vertical range from 4 km to 25 km with the separation between two tangent altitudes of 1km.
- Simulations performed any 50 km along track and 25 km across track.
- NESR and calibration errors are applied to the spectra before the retrieval procedure.

The TDS products produced for the simulations for CAIRT will be stored in ASCII format. The products are then used by the GBB_clouds code with a retrieval procedure described in Papandrea et al., 2025.

The file name follows this structure:

sim_ <actrack>_seq_ <c_seq>.dat

where

- **<actrack>**: is the across track position of the corresponding column of the detector array (1 is the leftmost column – a table with the corresponding longitude will be included in the delivered dataset)
- **<c_seq>**: is the number of the considered acquisition (a table with the correspondence of this number with the along track geolocation will be included in the delivered dataset)

Table 2 shows the file structure, comprehensive of the header lines.

Table 2. Structure of the output file

Header 1 (2 rows)
Header 2 → N. of spectral data points
Header 3
Header 4 → N. of simulated tangent altitudes
Header 5 (3 rows)
Header 6 (N. of simulated sweeps rows) → Tang. height [km] & orbital coord. [deg.] of sweeps
Header 7

Spectral point number	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Intensity for sweep 1 (nW/(sr cm ² cm ⁻¹))	Intensity for sweep 2 (nW/(sr cm ² cm ⁻¹))	...	Intensity for sweep N (nW/(sr cm ² cm ⁻¹))
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NOTE : Only for the dataset produced for sensitivity studies: to speed up computation time, in case a LOS does not intersect any cloud, the spectra are not simulated, and negative intensity values are stored in the output file. In this case, the corresponding LOS simulated for clear sky scenarios should be used.

2 Literature

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